

IMAGERY-BASED RIVERSCAPES CONDITION & TREND MONITORING

PROTOCOL DEVELOPMENT & TESTING

Photo: Shoshone Creek, Idaho, May 2022. Credit: Cashe Rasmussen

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

PACFISH/INFISH Biological Opinion Monitoring Program (PIBO) is an extensive site-scale monitoring program designed to evaluate stream and riparian habitats in the interior Columbia and upper Missouri River basins. The program aims to evaluate habitat status (i.e., current condition) and trends, including the effects of livestock grazing on stream ecosystems.

The current PIBO protocol is difficult to nearly impossible to carry out at beaver-impacted reaches; beaver dam ponds are often unwadeable, and the number and diversity of channels in multithreaded rivers are difficult to capture with transect measurements.

This study evaluated an imagery-based method for assessing beaver dams and large wood impacts on stream reaches. Specifically, our data collection approach was based on aerial photo interpretation and digitization of drone aerial photography to capture inundation extent and type mapping (free flowing, overflow, and ponded) and floodplain land cover mapping (riparian vs. upland encroachment). The imagery-based approach allowed for data collection at the valley bottom scale, providing critical insights into riverscape health. The key indicators of riverscape health assessed included:

1. What proportion of valley bottom is active channel?
2. What proportion of valley bottom is inundated?
3. What proportion of valley bottom is riparian vs. upland?
4. How many channel confluences and difluences are there?
5. What is the total length of stream channels?
6. How many beaver dams and wood jams are there?

We applied the imagery-based protocol to two beaver-impacted PIBO reaches: Wildhorse Creek and Shoshone Creek. Key findings for Wildhorse Creek indicated that the site is in good geomorphic condition, with high levels of riparian vegetation, substantial secondary channel length, diverse inundation types, and high structural counts at both low and high flows. These results suggest high floodplain connectivity during both lower and higher flow periods. The results for Shoshone Creek closely reflected its semi-arid setting. The reach is simplified at lower flows but appeared to be in good geomorphic condition at higher flows when our metrics indicated high levels of floodplain connectivity.

This study demonstrates the utility of drone imagery for monitoring riverscapes and highlights the importance of structural complexity in maintaining riverscape health. While we see drone imagery and digitizing this imagery as useful monitoring tools, we recognize that there are many barriers to their effective implementation including pilot licensing, bureaucratic permitting pathways, and equipment costs. Even when drone imagery is successfully captured, the processing stage is time-consuming and prone to errors, such as image distortion and color shifts, which complicate the digitizing process. As with any manual data collection, mapping results will vary depending on the digitizer's knowledge of riverscape process and experience with GIS software and imagery interpretation. Despite these challenges, it is important to recognize that most monitoring approaches face similar administrative and technical obstacles. Ultimately, the value of high-quality monitoring data far exceeds that of logistical challenges.

The bottom line is that the imagery-based protocol proved to be an effective alternative to the current PIBO protocol, which is difficult to implement in beaver-impacted areas. The insights gained here will be used to inform PIBO, improving the assessment of beaver impoundments and multithreaded channels' impacts on riverscape conditions.

INTRODUCTION

PIBO was developed to monitor bull trout and steelhead habitat status and trends in the upper Columbia River basin (Saunders et al., 2019). The protocol includes extensive vegetation and channel field measurements that are used to track site habitat suitability and riverscape health over time. However, the current PIBO protocol is difficult to carry out at beaver-impacted reaches; beaver dam ponds are often unwadeable, and the number and diversity of channels in multithreaded rivers are difficult to capture with transect measurements (Scott & Collins, 2019). Additionally, the field-sourced metrics that PIBO collects may not adequately describe the hydrologic and geomorphic trends and processes that form the foundation of fluvial ecosystems (Fryirs, 2015; Kondolf & Micheli, 1995; Scott & Collins, 2019).

Our understanding of healthy riverscapes has recently evolved from a focus on universally single-threaded meandering streams to include a variety of multithreaded channel forms (Cluer & Thorne, 2014; Powers et al., 2019; Simon & Hupp, 1987; Skidmore & Wheaton, 2022). Both fish habitat suitability and riverscape complexity are linked to the presence of structures like large wood and beaver dams (Bouwes et al., 2016; Gurnell et al., 2002; Lonzarich & Quinn, 2011; Skidmore & Wheaton, 2022; Zalewski et al., 2003). An ideal monitoring protocol would be able to adequately describe structural complexity and its associated channel forms (Fryirs, 2015; Kondolf & Micheli, 1995). Given these developments, a monitoring project that covers a large area and diversity of streams, such as PIBO, would benefit from a monitoring protocol that can be applied to both the simplest and most complex riverscapes. Such a protocol would allow for robust comparison between reaches of differing complexity as well as tracking a restoration reach's trajectory from an incised, single-threaded meander, to a Stage 0, anastomosing beaver complex (Cluer & Thorne, 2014; Powers et al., 2019; Scott & Collins, 2019; Simon & Hupp, 1987).

Because field work data is often insufficient to accurately characterize complex riverscapes (Powers et al., 2019; Scott & Collins, 2019), we developed and tested a monitoring and assessment protocol to explore the utility of drone-based monitoring in complex riverscapes. The imagery-based protocol includes:

1. Site selection
2. Imagery capture using an unmanned aerial system (UAS)
3. Riverscape mapping (digitizing)
4. Geometric analyses of mapped layers

To test how effectively the imagery-based protocol can be used to compare data capture events for PIBO study sites, we took repeated imagery of two geomorphically and ecologically diverse stream reaches and conducted several analyses by comparing data from each site's low and higher flow season. We analyzed four metrics—valley bottom landcover, channel network organization, inundation and its hydraulic properties, and structural complexity—that are understood to reflect overall habitat availability and hydrologic resilience (Bouwes et al., 2016; Cluer & Thorne, 2014; Remiszewski et al., 2024; Skidmore & Wheaton, 2022; Wohl, 2021).

The landcover analysis classified the riverscape into riparian vegetation, upland vegetation, and channel cover classes based on the premise that hydrologically connected riverscapes would have high proportions of riparian vegetation and channel cover relative to upland vegetation cover (Macfarlane, Gilbert, et al., 2017; Macfarlane, McGinty, et al., 2017; Remiszewski et al., 2024). This is due to the influence of alluvial groundwater levels on vegetation types; since riparian vegetation requires saturated soils (Gregory et al., 1991; Macfarlane, Gilbert, et al., 2017; Remiszewski et al., 2024; Westbrook et al., 2006; Wohl, 2021), a high proportion of riparian vegetation in the valley bottom reflects a water table that is elevated over a large extent.

The channel network analysis quantifies primary and secondary channel lengths as well as confluences and difluences within the network. The spatial and hydraulic heterogeneity associated with complex channel networks is another indicator of riverscape connectivity and habitat diversity (Brierley & Fryirs, 2013; Cluer & Thorne, 2014; Powers et al., 2019; Wohl, 2021). Multi-threaded channels provide a diversity of habitats to aquatic organisms at various life stages

(Bouwes et al., 2016; Powers et al., 2019; Remiszewski et al., 2024). The confluences and diffluences associated with branching and merging channels introduce diverse geomorphic units like pools, riffles, and bars (Duncan et al., 2009; Wheaton et al., 2015). The extent and length of secondary channels reflects a riverscape's ability to distribute large floods across the valley bottom, reducing and diversifying total stream power and promoting sediment and nutrient storage (Powers et al., 2019; Scott & Collins, 2019; Westbrook et al., 2006).

The inundation analysis was based on previous work by Bartelt (2021) and uses surface area coverage of free flowing, ponded, and overflowing waters to assess water residence time. Free flowing water is unobstructed channel flow, ponded flow is any structurally-forced backwater, and over flowing water is flow located outside of the active channel such as high flow floodplain inundation or structurally forced spillover (Wheaton et al., 2015). Hydraulic diversity creates pool and backwater refugia for macroinvertebrates and juvenile fish (Bouwes et al., 2016; Bush & Wissinger, 2016; Lonzarich & Quinn, 2011; Remiszewski et al., 2024). Floodplain inundation drives deposition and retention of sediments, organic matter, and moisture that fosters robust riparian forests, making it a hallmark of floodplain connectivity (Bartelt, 2021; Gregory et al., 1991; Macfarlane, Gilbert, et al., 2017; Remiszewski et al., 2024; Westbrook et al., 2006; Wohl, 2021).

The structural complexity analysis describes the spatial distribution and densities of several varieties of channel structures—wood, emergent rocks, and woody vegetation—as well as the characteristics and stability of dams within beaver dam complexes for each study site. Structural complexity provides a wide variety of benefits for riverscape ecogeomorphic processes. Large wood creates refugia habitat for a variety of aquatic organisms from primary producers to piscivores (Abbe & Montgomery, 2003; Bush & Wissinger, 2016; Gregory et al., 1991; Scott & Collins, 2019; Zalewski et al., 2003), and contributes to geomorphic and hydraulic complexity through the formation of backwaters, plunge pools, and depositional zones (Abbe & Montgomery, 2003; Gregory et al., 1991; Gurnell et al., 2002; Montgomery et al., 2003; Wheaton et al., 2015; Wohl, 2013). Inorganic structures such as emergent rocks are helpful indicators of substrate mobility and macroinvertebrate habitat availability (Hussain & Pandit, 2012). In-channel vegetation can reflect low inundation frequency for vegetated channel segments or intermittent and ephemeral streams (Sargeant & Macfarlane, 2023).

The beaver dam analysis included counts and status assessments for dam structures within each site. Monitoring and assessing beaver dam complexes is essential to understanding riverscapes at a reach scale due to their heavy modification of local hydrology (Grudzinski et al., 2020; Larsen et al., 2021; Westbrook et al., 2006; Wohl, 2021), geomorphology (Larsen et al., 2021; Naiman et al., 2024; Westbrook et al., 2006; Wohl, 2021), vegetation communities (Remiszewski et al., 2024; Wohl, 2021), habitat and food availability (Bouwes et al., 2016; Bush & Wissinger, 2016; Larsen et al., 2021; Remiszewski et al., 2024), and nutrient cycling (Larsen et al., 2021; Skidmore & Wheaton, 2022; Wohl, 2021). Beaver dams and dam complexes enhance nutrient, sediment, and moisture retention by impounding and flooding large areas of riverscape (Gregory et al., 1991; Naiman et al., 2024; Wohl, 2021), and can further introduce geomorphic and structural complexity when they are destroyed by large floods, releasing pulses of wood, sediment, and organic matter into high flows (Hafen et al., 2020; Larsen et al., 2021; Wohl, 2021).

This report begins with a brief description of the study sites selected for this assessment, Wildhorse Creek and Shoshone Creek, Idaho. The descriptions are followed by a methods section that outlines the riverscape metrics that we mapped and the analyses that we conducted on those mapped layers. In the results section, we present the outputs from our analyses of landcover, channel networks, inundation, and structural complexity. Due to the difference between the two study sites, we show the data for each site separately. The discussion includes a synthesis of relevant findings for each site and outlines the advantages of the imagery-based riverscapes monitoring protocol. The report ends with a conclusion that describes the challenges of imagery-based monitoring and highlights relevant developments in remote sensing.

METHODS

STUDY SITES

The study sites for this riverscape scale analysis are two beaver-impacted reaches near the headwaters of Shoshone and Wildhorse Creeks located in southern and central Idaho, respectively (Figure 1). We chose these sites because they are in different ecoregions and landscape settings and tests whether the imagery-based riverscapes monitoring protocol can be applied to a range of diverse riverscapes. The extent and magnitude of impoundments and channel formation that beaver dams can facilitate largely depend on the physical characteristics of the surrounding landscape (Hafen et al., 2020; Larsen et al., 2021; Wohl, 2021). Valley bottom width and topography, stream channel size and slope, and seasonal flow regime determine the power and breadth of streamflow, and because dams are structurally compromised (i.e. 'blown-out') by strong flows, stream power limits when, where, and how beaver can build (Bartelt, 2021; Macfarlane, Wheaton, et al., 2017). According to recent literature, beaver have been observed to build dams in three primary settings: *classic*, with occasional to pervasive dam density only on the riverscape's primary channels; *steep*, small streams with a gradient >6%; and *floodplain*, where complexes are constructed on secondary channels or directly on the floodplain because dams are impossible on the primary channel due to channel size or stream power (Bartelt, 2021; Macfarlane, Wheaton, et al., 2017; Wohl, 2013) Our two study sites can be categorized into this primary settings framework.

Shoshone Creek

Shoshone Creek is a well-developed classic setting (Figure 2) with a typical primary channel width between 2 and 6 meters. The 505-meter stream reach is approximately 1800 meters above sea level with a slope of .010 and sinuosity of 1.17. The reach flows through silicic Miocene volcanic tuffs that are undergoing Basin and Range extensional faulting (Williams et al., 2016). The creek is located in the Northern Basin and Range level III ecoregion which is characterized as a cold desert with sagebrush steppe or saltbush vegetation and cool season grasses. Much of the region is used as rangeland (US EPA, 2015).

Wildhorse Creek

Wildhorse Creek is a floodplain setting (Figure 2) with a primary channel width generally between 10 and 15 meters. The 720-meter gravel-bedded stream reach is embedded in a glacial valley in the Sawtooth Mountains is approximately 2300 meters above sea level with a slope of 0.021 and sinuosity of 1.16. and flows through Paleoproterozoic gneissic rocks (Wilson & Skipp, 1994). The reach lies on a footwall just upstream of a low angle normal fault and is flanked to the south by a complex of normal and thrust faults. The creek is located in the Idaho Batholith level III ecoregion which is characterized as a western cordillera with conifer forests composed of Douglas-fir, Engelmann spruce, and subalpine fir. Common land uses in this region include logging, grazing, recreation and mining (US EPA, 2015).

Figure 1: The two study sites: PIBO reaches along Shoshone Creek and Wildhorse Creek in southern and central Idaho.

Figure 2: Examples of the three primary beaver dam riverscape settings (From Bartelt, 2021).

DATA COLLECTION

The objective of this project was to develop and test a geomorphically and ecologically meaningful monitoring framework to evaluate condition and trend across entire valley bottom extends of beaver dam impacted streams. As such, we have developed an imagery-based approach to assess riverscape condition at the riverscape segment scale. Our data collection approach was based on aerial photo interpretation and digitization of drone aerial photography to capture inundation extent and type mapping (free flowing, overflow, and ponded) and floodplain mapping (riparian vs. upland encroachment). Our approach focused on tracking inundation type and area; because these are important indicators of riverscape health that are directly modified by large wood and beaver dams. The percent and type of valley bottom inundation and/or riparian vs. upland not only are direct measures of the quantity of aquatic habitat present within the stream corridor but can be viewed as proxies for hydrogeomorphic and ecological characteristics and processes that are essential to riverscape health such as channel floodplain connectivity and water residence time.

An FAA licensed drone pilot collected full coverage orthomosaic images for each of the two PIBO sites at low and high flow discharge. With these sets of orthomosaic images, we were able to assess geomorphic and floodplain changes as well as changes in lateral connectivity associated with changes in discharge. Specifically, we assessed:

1. Valley bottom extent,
2. Active channel extent,
3. Number of high flow channels vs. low flow channels,
4. Inundation extent (surface water area) and type mapping (free flowing, overflow, and ponded),

5. Riparian vs. upland vegetation within valley bottom, and
6. Count and condition of beaver dams and wood jams (Table 1).

Table 1: Data collected to evaluate riverscape status and trend.

Variable	Method	Description
Valley bottom extent	Desktop	Used aerial imagery to delineate valley bottom extent.
Surface water extent and channel width	Desktop	Used aerial imagery to digitize surface water extent and active channel widths and compared their extents through time.
Channel network	Desktop	Used aerial imagery to assess number of channels and total channel length and compared through time.
Inundation extent and type mapping	Desktop/Field	Used aerial imagery and field observations to delineate inundation extent and type mapping (free flowing, overflow, and ponded) and compared their extents through time.
Riparian/upland vegetation cover	Desktop/Field	Used aerial imagery and field observations to delineate upland and riparian vegetation cover and compared their extents through time.
Beaver dams, natural structures, and wood accumulations	Desktop	Used aerial imagery to count and document the condition (intact, breached, blown-out), of beaver dams, natural structures, and wood accumulation and compared through time.

Valley Bottom and Valley Bottom Centerline

The valley bottom for each study site was delineated using aerial imagery. The resulting valley bottom polygon represents the maximum plausible floodable area within the contemporary flood regime. The valley bottom extent also represents the maximum riparian area and the maximum extent that can be influenced by restoration structures or beaver dams. Once the valley bottom polygon was produced a valley bottom centerline was generated which is a line that runs down the center of a valley bottom dividing a valley bottom into two equal halves.

Landcover

A valley bottom can be separated into three main components to develop a rough estimate of geomorphic activity and floodplain connectivity. Those components are (1) active channel, (2) riparian vegetation, and (3) upland vegetation encroachment.

Active Channel

The active channel is the area that is currently being reworked by scouring and depositional stream processes. It includes backwaters (e.g. ponds), free-flowing sections, unvegetated bars, and dry channel bed areas that are below the bankfull elevation and was digitized using drone imagery and QGIS spatial software.

Riparian/Upland Vegetation Cover

Portion of the valley bottom that are riparian or non-riparian were delineated as a polygon using imagery. The combined extents of active channel, riparian and upland equate to the total extent of the valley bottom. This data collected at the scale of the valley bottom provides critical insight into riverscape health, such as the ratio of riparian area to valley bottom area.

Channel Network

In addition to the channel-spanning polygon layer, a channel segment line network and confluence/diffuence point dataset were generated for each site to capture smaller scale channel complexity and habitat availability than can be accurately mapped by the polygon layer at each site's optimal mapping resolution (Wildhorse 1:250, Shoshone 1:250).

Inundation Extent and Type

Similar to the active channel, the inundated area can be delineated as a polygon using imagery. Additional categorization of the inundated area into free-flowing (i.e. un-impounded), backwater (e.g. beaver ponds) and overbank flow (i.e. sheetflow) can provide further insights into lateral connectivity an important indicator of riverscape health.

Inundated area is defined as the surface water extent at the time of data collection and therefore is directly related to the discharge at that time. For instance, an inundated area polygon generated during high flow will have a greater area than the same riverscape at low flow conditions. As such, inundated area should be measured at low flow and high flow conditions. During high flows the inundated area is likely to exceed the area of the active channel when flows are overbank and on the floodplain. During low flow the inundated area may likely be less than the active channel, as unvegetated bars are exposed.

Structural Complexity

To capture each beaver dam, we traced the crest of each dam. We also categorized each beaver dam as either intact, breached, or blown-out. Intact refers to a dam that is not structurally damaged. Breached is where the dam is still ponding water but is structurally damaged resulting in a lowered water level. A blown-out beaver dam is where there is structural damage to the dam that spans the full height of the dam.

Other mapped structures include large wood, live plants growing in the channel, and inorganic structures (typically emergent rocks). These structures were identified based on their ability to alter flow via shunting, impounding, and

accelerating flow and were mapped as points. Wood jams are large accumulations of large wood and were digitized as polygons due to their areal extent and tendency to grow and shrink with various flooding events.

DATA ANALYSIS

Four analyses were conducted on each site to quantify essential riverscape metrics—active channel, vegetation cover, channel networks, inundation, and structural complexity—and changes in those metrics over time and comparing high and low flows.

Landcover

We used QGIS area calculations to quantify the proportion of valley bottom that is occupied by the active channel at low and higher flows. The difference between the flows was visualized and quantified by a rasterized polygon overlay workflow, highlighting areas of channel expansion and narrowing. This same raster overlay was used to quantify shifts in the vegetation cover classes.

Although we did not expect significant riparian expansion or upland encroachment within the two-year time frame analyzed here, the proportion of the valley bottom occupied by riparian vegetation offers insight into longer-term riverscape connectivity. We used QGIS area calculations to quantify the proportion of valley bottom that is occupied by riparian and upland vegetation at low and higher flows. The difference between the flows was visualized and quantified by a rasterized polygon overlay workflow, highlighting areas of channel expansion – where riparian areas convert to part of the stream channel, riparian encroachment – where stream channel area converts to riparian habitat, riparian expansion – where the riparian forest expands into upland areas, and upland encroachment – where upland vegetation overtakes riparian areas.

Channel Network

Channel segment layers were stratified into ‘primary’ and ‘secondary’ channels and summarized by QGIS length calculations. Another important channel metric is channel merging and splitting (i.e., confluences and difluences, respectively). We quantified this with mapped point counts. This numerical analysis is supplemented by a side-by-side visual comparison of low/high flow channel network mapping and measurements for each site.

Inundation Extent and Type

To characterize inundation extent, we used QGIS area calculations to quantify the proportion of valley bottom that was inundated at low and higher flows. Since inundation is the primary connector between channel and floodplain processes, we also calculated the proportional inundation of the active channel as well as the floodplain—any part of the valley bottom that is not active channel.

Inundation type for each flow was summarized proportionally to show the change in hydraulic habitat diversity and availability between lower and higher flows.

Structural Complexity

Beaver dam counts and condition assessment were directly compared between low and higher flows. We visualized the results using bar charts. This workflow and visualization were repeated for the large wood, live, and inorganic structures. The wood jam calculations were analyzed by an additional surface area comparison.

RESULTS

Because the two study sites are very different riverscapes, both geomorphically and ecologically, we conducted the analyses at the site scale. The results are presented separately for each study reach.

WILDHORSE CREEK

The analyses for Wildhorse Creek highlighted the seasonal impact of beaver dams in a wide, floodplain context (Bartelt, 2021) valley bottom. Overall, indicators of riverscape health—including secondary channel activation and floodplain inundation—increase drastically at high flows. The Wildhorse Creek reach also provided an opportunity to track the impacts of a channel-spanning wood jam at its upstream end that appears to be produced by debris from a recent avalanche. In short, the Wildhorse study site is a structurally rich, well-connected riverscape that is likely to expand further into low-lying upland areas due to its ability to widely distribute seasonal high flows across the valley bottom.

Landcover

The high resolution landcover mapping outputs for the Wildhorse Creek reach are summarized in Table 2 and shown in Figure 3. The site is dominated by riparian vegetation (about 50% of the valley bottom for both low and high flow discharge) with some upland conifers growing within the active floodplain and on vegetated islands.

Figure 4 shows the expansion and narrowing of Wildhorse Creek’s landcover classes between 2021 and 2023. Most channel expansion occurred upstream of beaver dams and behind a large wood accumulation (i.e. wood jam) at the reach’s upstream end. There are also instances of riparian island erosion inside of the main channel at the downstream end as well as a large channel erosion event at the very upstream end. Most riparian expansion – typically characterized by conifer dieback – occurred on vegetated islands and behind the wood jam at the reach’s upstream end. Riparian encroachment (i.e. channel narrowing) is likely due to riparian colonization of depositional bars or variations in mapping approaches between imagery capture dates (Table 2).

Table 2: Landcover change statistics for Wildhorse Creek.

	Area (m ²)	% of Valley Bottom
Channel Expansion (Riparian to Channel)	2456.38	3.77%
Upland Erosion (Upland to Channel)	5.83	0.01%
Riparian Encroachment (Channel to Riparian)	621.04	0.95%
Riparian Expansion (Upland to Riparian)	56.83	0.09%
Persistent Channel	11864.73	18.2%
Persistent Riparian	32242.62	49.4%
Persistent Upland	17992.81	27.6%

Figure 3: Landcover mapping for Wildhorse Creek at low flow (top) and higher flow (bottom).

Figure 4: Landcover changes between low and higher flow for Wildhorse Creek

Channel Network

The high-resolution channel network mapping outputs for the Wildhorse reach are shown in Table 3, Figure 5, and Figure 6. There is a large difference in confluences and diffluences and channel segment length between high and low flow. High flow shows almost 5 times as many confluences and 7 times as many diffluences as low flow. Additionally, high flow exhibits 24 areas where the channels show both merging and splitting qualities (recorded as “C/D” in Table 3, Figure 5, and Figure 6). At high flow, secondary channel length more than triples compared to low flow and accounts for over 85% of total channel length. At low flow, secondary channel length accounts for almost 65% of total channel length. Overall, channel length increases by 135% from low to high flow with minimal difference in primary channel lengths.

The density of network complexity on the channel-adjacent floodplain reflects the secondary channel activation associated with seasonal high flows in healthy riverscapes. Another potential mechanism for this complex secondary channel network is beaver activity which includes dam building as well as channel digging for transport between ponds (Grudzinski et al., 2020). It is likely that many of the smaller secondary channels occurred as a result of this digging behavior and that fluvial erosional processes may widen and extend them in the future.

Table 3. Channel network statistics for Wildhorse Creek.

	Low Flow	Higher Flow	Change at High Flow
Channel Length	2277.5 m	5348.2 m	+ 135 %
<i>Primary</i>	821.9 m	763.1 m	- 7 %
<i>Secondary</i>	1455.6 m	4585.0 m	+ 215 %
# of Confluences	34	160	+ 371 %
# of Diffluences	19	134	+ 605 %
# of C/D's	0	24	N/A

Figure 5: Channel segments and confluence/diffuence mapping for Wildhorse Creek at low flow (top) and higher flow (bottom).

Figure 6: Comparison of channel segments and confluences/diffuences between lower (left) and higher (right) flows at Wildhorse Creek.

Inundation Extent and Type

The high-resolution inundation and structure mapping outputs and calculations for the Wildhorse Creek reach are shown in Table 4 and Figure 7. High flow in Wildhorse Creek ends up filling nearly the entire active channel (99%) while low flow fills approximately 68% of the active channel. Even at low flow, beaver dams and the previously highlighted wood jam facilitate overbank flooding with 1.74% of the floodplain inundated. At high flow, floodplain inundation increases tenfold with 18.5% of the floodplain inundated.

The structural forcing behind the Wildhorse study site's considerable floodplain connectivity is evidenced by the higher flow's hydraulic characteristics. At high flow, ponded inundation makes up about 26% of the total inundation compared to about 16% at low flow (Table 4, Figure 8). Similarly, overflow inundation composes about 27% of the total inundation at high flow and about 17% at low flow (Table 4, Figure 8). These patterns reflect how structures and beaver dams impound and laterally spread water across the floodplain.

Table 4: Inundation analysis calculations for Wildhorse Creek. Inundation extent proportions are calculated as proportion of the total valley bottom, active channel, and floodplain areas while inundation type proportions are calculated as proportion of total inundation extent.

	Low Flow	High Flow	Change at High Flow
Inundation Extent			
% Valley Bottom Inundation	14.2 %	32.2 %	+ 127.1 %
% Channel Inundation	67.5 %	99.3 %	+ 47.1 %
% Floodplain Inundation	1.74 %	18.5 %	+ 968.0 %
Inundation Type			
% Ponded	15.9 %	25.9 %	+ 63.3 %
% Free-Flowing	67.4 %	46.8 %	- 30.6 %
% Overflow	16.7 %	27.3 %	+ 63.3 %

Figure 7: Inundation extent/type and structure mapping for Wildhorse Creek at low flow (top) and higher flow (bottom).

Figure 8: Inundation extent and type for low (Left) and higher (right) flows at Wildhorse Creek. The stacked bar chart in the middle of the figure shows each inundation type as a proportion of total inundation area.

Structural Complexity

In addition to inundation, Figure 7 shows the mapping of various flow-altering structures for Wildhorse Creek. Structure counts for both flow conditions are shown in Table 5. Under low-flow conditions, live structures (Figure 9) and inorganic structures (e.g. emergent rocks) (Figure 10) are more likely to be visible from aerial imagery, resulting in a notable difference between the amount marked for 2021 versus 2023. Under high-flow conditions, the river is capable of transporting more large wood. This is reflected in the 2023 imagery with the larger presence of large wood in the channel, along with an 86% increase in the surface area of wood jams (Figure 11). The number of visible beaver dams is about 30% greater during low flow (Figure 12).

Table 5: Structure statistics for Wildhorse Creek at low and higher flow.

	Low Flow	High Flow	Change at High Flow
Structure Counts			
Live	29	16	- 45 %
Inorganic	175	27	- 85 %
Wood Jams	1	4	+ 300 %
Large wood	92	113	+ 23 %
Wood Jam Surface Area			
	259.0 m ²	482.3 m ²	+ 86 %
Beaver Dams			
Intact	13	9	- 31 %
Breached	0	0	none
Blown out	2	1	- 50 %

Live Structures

The distribution of live vegetation structures for low and higher flow at Wildhorse Creek is shown in Figure 9. We measured a large decrease in live structures in the higher flow data. This pattern is likely caused by higher water levels either scouring out or submerging woody vegetation. The large wood jam at the reach's upstream end impounded a significant amount of flow which submerged many of the live structures in this portion of the reach.

Figure 9: Heatmap and chart map of live vegetation (live structures) counts within Wildhorse Creek's active channel at low (left) and higher (right) flow. The heatmap shows point density per 10m² (see the legend on the far right for color values). Beaver dams are mapped as dotted green, orange, and red lines.

Inorganic Structures

The distribution of inorganic structures (i.e. emergent rocks) for low and higher flow at Wildhorse Creek is shown in Figure 10. We measured a significant decrease in inorganic structures at high flow which is primarily due to higher water levels submerging the structures.

Figure 10: Heatmap and bar chart of emergent rock (inorganic structures) count within Wildhorse Creek's active channel at low (left) and higher (right) flow. The heatmap – which is clipped to the active channel extent – shows point density per 10m² (see the legend on the far right for color values). Beaver dams are mapped as dotted green, orange, and red lines.

Wood Jams

The distribution of large wood accumulations (i.e. wood jams) for low and higher flow at Wildhorse Creek is shown in Figure 11. In the lower flow data, a single large jam spans the main channel at the upstream end. Higher flows appear to have transported much large wood from upstream that was eventually caught by the initial wood jam. This resulted in an 86% increase in surface area over the two-year period between the low flow data capture (2021) and the higher flow data capture (2023).

Figure 11: Heatmap and bar chart of log jam counts (dark brown) and jam surface area (light brown) within Wildhorse Creek's active channel at low (left) and higher (right) flow. The heatmap—which is clipped to the active channel extent—shows point density per 10m² (see the legend on the far right for color values). Beaver dams are mapped as dotted green, orange, and red lines.

Large Wood

The distribution of large wood in the active channel for low and higher flow at Wildhorse creek is shown in Figure 12. Between lower and higher flow, there is a 23% increase. At higher flow, the highest density of large wood in the primary channel lies above the wood jam(s) at the site's upstream end. Large wood was deposited due to the impoundment caused by the jam, but the large wood was not transported with the force necessary to be incorporated into the jam structures. The other mechanisms for large wood increases appear to be channel expansion and tree falls. There is a large amount of dead wood on the floodplain and the surrounding hillslopes, especially at the site's upstream end. Imagery from Google Earth Pro (*Google Earth Pro*, 2024) indicates that much of the wood in the upstream end was introduced by an avalanche that occurred between 2014 and 2017. In areas where the channel has laterally eroded into the floodplain, large wood on those surfaces becomes incorporated into the stream and is eventually transported through the system. In addition to fallen logs, there are many dead conifers standing near the banks in the 2021 imagery that appear to have fallen into the channel in the 2023 data.

Figure 12: Heatmap and bar chart of large wood within Wildhorse Creek's active channel at low (left) and higher (right) flow. The heatmap – which is clipped to the active channel extent – shows point density per 10m² (see the legend on the far right for color values). Beaver dams are mapped as dotted green, orange, and red lines.

Beaver Dams

We analyzed the beaver dam complexes both between low and higher flow years (Figure 13) and over the two years between data captures (Figure 14). We found a 31% reduction in intact beaver dams at higher flow (Table 5), indicating that seasonal flooding has sufficient stream power to reconfigure dam complexes. In Figure 14, we see that the majority of disappearing dams are located close to the primary channel, and that the complex's largest dams have not changed over the two-year time frame. These are expected patterns in a floodplain beaver dam complex. Stream power that blows out beaver dams decreases with lateral distance from the primary channel since friction on the floodplain surface effectively dilutes the force of the flow. This protects the core beaver dams and allows the complex to be stable through time.

Figure 13: Beaver dam counts and status for low (left) and higher (right) flow at Wildhorse Creek.

Figure 14: Map of changes in beaver dam presence or structural status at Wildhorse Creek between September 2021 (low flow) and June 2023 (higher flow).

Condition Assessment

The impacts of beaver activity are evident both within and outside of the channel. Thus, we analyze the geomorphic, hydraulic, and vegetative complexity of beaver impacted systems on a valley bottom scale. Tracking changes in metrics such as active channel and riparian areas as a proportion of total valley bottom area enables us to compare the proportional magnitude of beaver impacts within and between riverscapes over time. Such riverscape health status indicators are detailed in Table 6.

Table 6: Condition indicators for Wildhorse Creek at low flow and high flow.

Condition Indicator	Lower Flow	Higher Flow
<i>What proportion of valley bottom is active channel?</i>	19.1 %	22.0 %
<i>What proportion of valley bottom is inundated?</i>	14.2 %	32.2 %
<i>What proportion of valley bottom is riparian vs. upland?</i>	53.1 % v. 27.8 %	52.6 % v. 25.5 %
<i>How many stream channels are there?</i>	36	194
<i>What is the total length of stream channels?</i>	2277.5 m	5348.2 m
<i>How many beaver dams and wood jams are there?</i>	beaver dams: 13 wood jams: 1	beaver dams: 10 wood jams: 4

Due to a lack of obvious abandoned floodplain terraces, the reach does not appear to have undergone any recent incision cycles. The numerous side channels and accessible floodplain effectively diffuse floods and allow a high nutrient cycling capacity (Cluer & Thorne, 2014; Wohl, 2021). Additionally, beaver activity promotes hydraulic diversity at low and higher flows (Figure 7, Figure 8), creating drought and flood refugia (Bartelt, 2021; Remiszewski et al., 2024). This combination of a complex stream network, floodplain inundation, and structural complexity at both low and higher flows indicate that the reach is in near reference condition (Cluer & Thorne, 2014).

SHOSHONE CREEK

As noted previously, the Shoshone Creek study site is located in a semi-arid watershed which, according to our analyses, can experience disconnected channel habitat when parts of the stream go dry in low flow periods. This study highlights the ability of instream structures like beaver dams to provide perennial habitat in a less-perennial system. Shoshone Creek also exhibits structurally driven secondary channel formation at high flows. Overall, the site shows the most complexity and geomorphic activity near its largest beaver dams on the downstream half, and its upland/riparian vegetation boundaries are fairly stable.

Landcover

The high resolution landcover mapping outputs for the Shoshone site are shown in Table 7 and Figure 15. The vegetation cover in this valley bottom shows almost even coverage between riparian (~ 40%) and upland areas (~ 45%) with pockets of relic willow inside of the upland areas. The active channel covers about 15.5% at low flow and about 16.6% at high flow.

Figure 16 shows the expansion and reduction of Shoshone Creek's landcover classes between 2021 and 2022. The raster overlay analysis showed channel expansion into riparian areas as the primary landcover shift between the two imagery capture dates. Most channel expansion occurred along the waterline of expanding beaver dam ponds and as a result of secondary channel formation/activation immediately downstream of beaver dams. There are also many instances of riparian island erosion inside of the main channel. Channel narrowing is likely due to riparian vegetation encroachment onto depositional bars or variations in mapping approaches between imagery capture dates.

Table 7: Landcover analysis statistics for Shoshone Creek.

	Area (m ²)	% of Valley Bottom
Channel Expansion (Riparian to Channel)	417.37	1.25 %
Upland Erosion (Upland to Channel)	0.00	0.00 %
Riparian Encroachment (Channel to Riparian)	26.81	0.08 %
Riparian Expansion (Upland to Riparian)	0.00	0.00 %
Persistent Channel	5160.74	15.4 %
Persistent Riparian	12828.67	38.4 %
Persistent Upland	14987.53	44.9 %

Figure 15: Landcover mapping for Shoshone Creek at low flow (top) and higher flow (bottom).

Figure 16: Landcover changes between low and higher flow for Shoshone Creek.

Channel Network

The high-resolution channel network mapping outputs for the Shoshone site are summarized in Table 8 and shown in Figure 17 and Figure 18. Table 8 Channel network statistics for Shoshone Creek. There is a large difference in confluences and diffluences and channel segment length between high and low flow. Higher flow shows almost twice as many confluences and diffluences as low flow. At low flow, secondary channel length accounts for about 22% of total channel length. At higher flow, secondary channel length more than doubles compared to low flow and accounts for about 40% of total channel length. Overall, channel length increases by 19.5% from low to high flow with minimal difference in primary channel lengths.

Essentially all of the secondary channel activation/formation that we documented at high flow was a result of large beaver dams. The dams laterally pushed high flows onto floodplain surfaces where the water accumulated into topographic lows and began flowing alongside the primary channel. Where high flows overtopped the dam crests, water plunging over the crests carved out small channels that eventually flowed inward to the primary channel.

Table 8 Channel network statistics for Shoshone Creek.

	Low Flow	High Flow	Change at High Flow
Channel Length	832.7 m	995.4 m	+ 19.5 %
<i>Primary</i>	584.6 m	538.9 m	- 7.8 %
<i>Secondary</i>	180.5 m	389.4 m	+ 115.8 %
<i>Tributary</i>	67.7 m	67.1 m	- 0.83 %
# of Confluences	7	12	+ 71.4 %
# of Diffluences	7	12	+ 71.4 %

Figure 17: Channel segments and confluence/diffluence mapping for Shoshone Creek at low flow (top) and higher flow (bottom).

Figure 18: Comparison of channel segments and confluences/difluences between lower (left) and higher (right) flows at Wildhorse Creek.

Inundation Extent and Type

The high-resolution inundation and structure mapping outputs and calculations for the Shoshone site are shown in Table 9 and Figure 19. Higher flow in Shoshone fills 92.3% of the active channel, and low flow fills approximately 26% of the active channel. At low flow there is essentially no floodplain inundation, and at higher flow, approximately 3.5% of the floodplain is inundated—a 5783% increase.

Beaver dam ponds appear to play a large role in this site’s ability to sustain aquatic habitat. At low flow, when only 25% of the channel is inundated, beaver dam ponds comprise almost 40% of the total inundated area and are nearly the only surface water available in the site’s downstream third (Figure 20). At higher flow, ponded water accounts for about half of the inundated area. At the Shoshone site, there is very little overflow at low flow (0.53% of total inundation). At higher flow, we measured a 2431% increase in overflow to 13.4% of total inundation, most of which resulted from beaver dams overtopping and spilling sheet flow onto the floodplain. The other instances of overflow were a small oxbow in the site’s upstream half and areas of unforced overbank flooding.

Table 9: Inundation statistics for Shoshone Creek. Inundation extent proportions are calculated as proportion of the total valley bottom, active channel, and floodplain areas while inundation type proportions are calculated as proportion of total inundation extent.

	Low Flow	High Flow	Change at High Flow
Inundation Extent			
% Valley Bottom Inundation	4.02 %	11.7 %	+ 191 %
% Channel Inundation	25.7 %	92.3 %	+ 259 %
% Floodplain Inundation	0.06 %	3.53 %	+ 5783 %
Inundation Type			
% Ponded	39.5 %	49.4 %	+ 25.1 %
% Free-Flowing	60.0 %	37.3 %	- 37.9 %
% Overflow	0.53 %	13.4 %	+ 2431 %

Figure 19: Inundation extent/type and structure mapping for Shoshone Creek at low flow (top) and higher flow (bottom).

Figure 20: Inundation extent and type for low (left) and higher (right) flows at Shoshone Creek. The stacked bar chart in the middle of the figure shows each inundation type as a proportion of total inundation area. The stream is flowing from bottom to top.

Structural Complexity

Structure mapping for Shoshone Creek at low and higher flows is shown in Figure 19. We measured a decrease in live structures at higher flow (Figure 21) and an increase in inorganic structures (e.g. emergent rocks) (Figure 22). At higher flow, we measured the emergence of two wood jams that were not present at low flow (Figure 23). Large wood saw little change in count or spatial distribution between flows (Figure 24). The total number of observed beaver dam crests observed was equal between low and higher flows, but the intactness of the dams varied slightly (Table 10, Figure 25). The appearance of blown-out dams corresponds to the damage that higher flows can inflict on dam complexes. The surrounding area for this site is comprised of sagebrush steppe, which is a poor contributor to large wood and other flow altering structures, resulting in beaver dams being the primary source of structural complexity.

Table 10: Structure statistics for Shoshone Creek at low and higher flow.

	Low Flow	High Flow	Change at High Flow
Structure Counts			
Live	53	47	- 11 %
Inorganic	1	3	+ 200 %
Wood Jams	1	3	+ 200 %
Large Wood	26	25	- 4 %
Log Jam Surface Area			
	3.8 m ²	12.8 m ²	+ 237 %
Beaver Dams			
Intact	8	9	+ 13 %
Breached	5	4	- 20 %
Blown out	0	1	NA

Live Structures

The distribution of live structures for low and higher flow at Shoshone creek is shown in Figure 21. We measured a slight decrease in live structures in the higher flow data which is primarily due to submergence of the willows and shrubs located in beaver dam ponds and scouring of vegetation off of point bars.

Figure 21: Heatmap and chart map of live vegetation (live structures) counts within Shoshone Creek's active channel at low (left) and higher (right) flow. The heatmap shows point density per 10m² (see the legend on the far right for color values).

Inorganic Structures

The distribution of inorganic structures (i.e. emergent rocks) for low and higher flow at Shoshone creek is shown in Figure 22. We measured two additional emergent rocks in the higher flow that were possibly unburied or transported by flooding.

Figure 22: Heatmap and bar chart of emergent rock (inorganic structures) count within Shoshone Creek's active channel at low (left) and higher (right) flow. The heatmap – which is clipped to the active channel extent – shows point density per 10m² (see the legend on the far right for color values).

Wood Jams

The distribution of woodjams for low and higher flow at Shoshone creek is shown in Figure 23. Large wood tends to accumulate on point bars or around small topographic highs located within the channel such as live structures or small, often vegetated, alluvial deposits. These jams are composed primarily of willow material which reflects the sparse forests of the area. The nearest living hard wood community is located on a hillslope almost a kilometer upstream.

Figure 23: Heatmap and bar chart of log jam counts (dark brown) and jam surface area (light brown) within Shoshone Creek's active channel at low (left) and higher (right) flow. The heatmap – which is clipped to the active channel extent – shows point density per 10m² (see the legend on the far right for color values).

Large Wood

The distribution of large wood for low and higher flow at Shoshone creek is shown in Figure 24. Between the low and higher flow imagery captures, 2021 and 2022 respectively, large wood counts and spatial distribution appear fairly consistent. In contrast to the site's wood jams, large wood is mostly composed of material from large fallen conifers that once occupied the floodplain. As indicated by Figure 24, the majority of this dead wood is found at the upstream end of the site, and it appears that the stream primarily recruits these logs via lateral channel expansion.

Figure 24: Heatmap and bar chart of large wood within Shoshone Creek's active channel at low (left) and higher (right) flow. The heatmap – which is clipped to the active channel extent – shows point density per 10m² (see the legend on the far right for color values).

Beaver Dams

We analyzed the beaver dam complexes both between low and higher flow years (Figure 25) and over the two years between data captures (Figure 26). At the second, higher flow, data capture we found a slight increase in intact beaver dams (Table 10), a 20% decrease in breached dams, and the appearance of a blown-out dam. These results along with Figure 26 indicate that the beaver dam complex sees a lot of turn over with higher flows frequently damaging and blowing out dams. The beaver population is actively building new dams and expanding older structures, mostly on the downstream half of the reach.

Figure 25: Beaver dam counts and status for low (left) and higher (right) flow at Wildhorse Creek.

Figure 26: Map of changes in beaver dam presence or structural status at Shoshone Creek between September 2021 (low flow) and May 2022 (higher flow).

Condition Assessment

The impacts of beaver activity are evident both within and outside of the channel. Thus, we analyze the geomorphic, hydraulic, and vegetative complexity of beaver impacted systems on a valley bottom scale. Tracking changes in metrics such as active channel and riparian areas as a proportion of total valley bottom area enables us to compare the proportional magnitude of beaver impacts within and between riverscapes over time. Such riverscape health status indicators are detailed in Table 11.

Table 11: Condition indicators for Shoshone Creek at low flow and high flow.

Condition Indicator	Low Flow	High Flow
What proportion of valley bottom is active channel?	15.5 %	16.7 %
What proportion of valley bottom is inundated?	14.2 %	32.2 %
What proportion of valley bottom is riparian vs. upland?	39.6 % v. 44.9 %	38.6 % v. 44.7 %
How many stream channels are there?	9	14
What is the total length of stream channels?	832.7 m	995.4 m
How many beaver dams and wood jams are there?	beaver dams: 13 wood jams: 1	beaver dams: 13 wood jams: 3

Tall cut banks and stands of relic willow within the upland vegetation zone indicate that the reach has experienced a reduction in floodplain connectivity likely caused by incision. This riverscape variety still exhibits the ecosystem services, floodplain connectivity, and habitat refugia of a reference condition riverscape, but in lower diversities and magnitudes (Cluer & Thorne, 2014). Shoshone Creek forms deep scour pool refugia on the outside of its meander bends (Figure 20) which provides essential drought refugia during the semi-arid system's dry season (Cluer & Thorne, 2014). Beaver dams provide similar drought refugia in the form of structurally forced ponding (Remiszewski et al., 2024). At higher flows, beaver activity within the reach allows the riverscape to effectively diffuse large floods, promoting flood resilience and refugia along with floodplain connectivity (Bouwes et al., 2016; Naiman et al., 2024; Wohl, 2021).

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates the utility of drones for monitoring riverscapes and highlights the importance of structural complexity in maintaining riverscape health. Drones offer significant advantages for spatial monitoring: imagery can be reviewed and maps edited as long as the data remains accessible, allowing for more time to fully analyze riverscape condition indicators. Additionally, drones enable the collection of data over a larger spatial extent, enhancing the scope of riverscape monitoring. By comparing data captured during low and high flow events at two distinct, beaver-impacted riverscapes, we observed substantial differences. In nearly all cases, indicators of riverscape complexity and resilience increased at higher flows. At both flow conditions and for both study reaches, floodplain inundation and secondary channel activation were strongly influenced by structural features such as beaver dams and wood jams. Drone imagery effectively captured these site-scale responses, providing valuable insights into how beaver activity and wood accumulation shape riverscapes.

The Wildhorse Creek reach, a coarse-bedded high mountain stream near the headwaters of the Big Lost River, is in near reference condition. At both low and higher flows, the valley bottom is morphologically complex and highly connected, with secondary channels and diverse hydraulic habitats such as ponded water and floodplain inundation. Wildhorse Creek is particularly notable for being a high-energy riverscape in a similarly high-energy landscape. The valley bottom morphology is largely shaped by fluvial erosion and inputs from avalanche debris. Even between our two data capture events (2021 and 2023), the main channel underwent measurable lateral expansion and island erosion. From the drone imagery, we observed numerous channel heads on the floodplain surfaces that reflect how frequently overflow drains off of the landscape, allowing secondary channels to expand and lengthen through head cutting and lateral expansion (Brierley & Fryirs, 2013). These head cuts are reflected in Wildhorse Creek's high confluence-diffuence ratio (Table 5). The largest changes were seen near the avalanche-formed wood jam at the top of the reach including active channel expansion, conifer dieback, wood accumulation, and floodplain inundation. The only status indicator not involved were beaver dams which were fairly consistent between the two data captures due to the protective nature of floodplain setting beaver dam complexes. The combination of these high-impact structural features--the wood jam and the beaver dam complex--results in a highly complex, resilient riverscape at low flow where we measured almost 1500 meters of active secondary channel and 14% valley bottom inundation. At higher flow, this complexity dramatically increased in most instances; wood jam and beaver activity caused impoundments and secondary channel activation/formation that inundated almost 20% of the floodplain and a third of the entire valley bottom. This overflow inundation carries moisture, nutrients, and sediments to floodplain soils and riparian forests that enable Wildhorse's large floodplain system to occupy almost half of its valley bottom and to persist into the dry season and through drought years (Larsen et al., 2021; Naiman et al., 2024; Remiszewski et al., 2024; Wohl, 2021). Wood jams and beaver dams also create diverse in-stream habitat throughout the hydrologic seasons by impounding large ponds and inundating smaller channels (Bartelt, 2021; Bouwes et al., 2016; Remiszewski et al., 2024; Westbrook et al., 2006).

In future years, we expect to see a measurable amount of riparian expansion into the upland zones. Beaver dams will likely contribute to this somewhat in the downstream half of the reach, but the primary driver of conifer die-off and riparian colonization will most likely be the impoundment behind the wood jam at the upstream end of the reach (Burchsted et al., 2010). The ponding behind the jam will drown-out upland conifers, and when the jam is eventually flushed downstream by a large flood the alluvial deposits left behind will likely become available for riparian species to populate (Abbe & Montgomery, 2003; Montgomery et al., 2003; Wohl, 2013). This dramatic increase in inundated area will raise the surrounding water table, spreading the same 'drowning' effect further than the impoundment's edge (Westbrook et al., 2006; Wohl, 2021). The hillslopes surrounding this study reach are covered with avalanche scars; avalanches appear to be a consistent mechanism for wood recruitment. Consistent wood recruitment combined with an active beaver population will enable the reach to maintain its structural complexity and resilience (Abbe & Montgomery, 2003; Larsen et al., 2021; Wohl, 2013, 2021).

The Shoshone Creek reach is notable for its significant variability in discharge, which is determined by its desert climate. This results in a system that tends to simplify in dry periods but has the potential for significant complexity during higher flows. A healthy desert riverscape would be resilient to both drought and intense high flows that characterize semi-arid regions (Remiszewski et al., 2024). While discontinuous inundation during low flows indicates room for improvement of drought resilience and continuous aquatic habitat, this site demonstrates resilience to high flow events, primarily due to beaver activity (Figure 19). Local wood sources are limited, consisting primarily of willow debris and dead logs on the floodplain. However, there is potential for upstream wood recruitment and transport into the reach via high flow events (Abbe & Montgomery, 2003; Wohl, 2013). This scarcity makes beaver dam structures critical for the system's complexity and resilience. During low flow periods, the dams account for 40% of total inundation and are the only source of hydraulically diverse aquatic habitat. At higher flows, dams are the main drivers of forced overflow and secondary channel formation/activation, increasing floodplain inundation from nearly 0% to almost 4% and effectively doubling the total length of secondary channels. Beaver dams are also heavily involved in this stream's erosional processes. Flow that spills over dam crests often carves out small secondary channels.

In the future, we would expect this process to continue along with lateral erosion as flow cuts to the side of dam crests and debris from blown-out and breached dams (Shahveredian et al., 2019). If these processes continue, beaver dams and meander bends will eventually widen the riparian area through lateral expansion evidenced by significant cutbanks and spillways observed downstream of the dams (Cluer & Thorne, 2014; Simon & Hupp, 1987). This lateral expansion will create new floodplain surfaces and side channels, which will enhance the structural complexity and resilience of the reach (Larsen et al., 2021; Wohl, 2013, 2021). Given the periodic destruction of these dams during high-flow events, it is likely that beaver activity in the reach will ebb and flow as the dam complex configuration shifts up and down the creek. The sediment deposits left behind blown-out dams will cycle in and out of floodplain and active channel classifications as dam sites are opportunistically revisited, promoting nutrient cycling, local groundwater storage, and aquatic habitat diversity and connectivity (Burchsted et al., 2010; Larsen et al., 2021; Westbrook et al., 2006; Wohl, 2021).

The common theme between the two study sites is that their resilience and complexity are driven by structural forcing. Introducing structures to simplified, degraded reaches is a common restoration strategy for increasing complexity and improving resilience. Since monitoring is a key aspect of restoration and conservation, it is essential to develop new monitoring protocols that accurately capture riverscape response to conserved and restored structural processes (Fryirs, 2015; Powers et al., 2019; Scott & Collins, 2019). UAV imagery provides high enough resolution to fully capture riverscape complexity at the reach scale. Digitizing riverscape features provides much of the same measurements as field-based transects but over a wider area and with more potential for quality control and insightful spatial analyses. A cursor can map several meters per second, moving over dam crests and through thickets of woody vegetation that would bar field crews from effective data collection. Protocols like the imagery-based riverscapes monitoring protocol also allow for data quality control since imagery can be reviewed and interpreted long after the data capture event. There are a few advantages to field measurements: drone imagery allows for lateral and longitudinal data collection but is rarely able to capture channel depth and discharge measurements that transects provide. Another difficulty with imagery-based monitoring is that vegetation cover can obscure important features that would be visible to field crews. But, when riverscapes are too complex to be accessed or interpreted by field measurement protocols, it is better to have drone data than no data.

This study used drone imagery and digitizing to quantify how low and higher flows travel through two distinct, structurally complex riverscapes. These same methods could be applied to compare even lower and higher flows to further measure the reaches' resilience to drought and flood or to compare geomorphically similar, but structurally starved reaches to the study sites monitored here. Perhaps most importantly, our analyses show that the imagery-based riverscapes monitoring protocol is applicable to riverscapes at varying complexities, meaning that the protocol can be applied to a number of comparative analyses, long term monitoring projects, and restoration project designs. Under most conditions, the planform view provided by drone imagery allows analyses to detect riverscape processes almost anywhere on the valley bottom surface. This data can be stored and recaptured over time, enhancing understanding of riverscapes across large areas and time periods.

CONCLUSION

Beaver reintroduction and low-tech process-based restoration (Shahverdian et al., 2019) are growing in popularity as restoration tools. While these approaches are grounded in solid observation and established river theory, the monitoring and assessment of such projects remain limited (Wohl, 2021). Funding for monitoring efforts is often scarce, and the complex riverscapes that the restoration creates are difficult to measure. In this report, we present and apply a drone-based monitoring method that circumvents many of the logistical difficulties associated with field measurements, offering a reach-scale assessment of riverscape form, complexity, and resilience. By using this approach, we were able to compare riverscape conditions under varying flow regimes and track changes over time. Our findings reinforce the notion that structural complexity is vital for promoting riverscape health and enhancing habitat diversity.

While we see drones and remote digitizing as useful monitoring tools, we recognize that there are many barriers to their effective implementation. Most restoration projects would require a licensed drone pilot and involve considerable bureaucratic hurdles. Recent federal policy prevents the use of Chinese-manufactured equipment in many land management projects, significantly increasing equipment costs. Even when drone imagery is successfully captured, the processing stage can be time-consuming and prone to errors, such as image distortion and color shifts, which complicate the digitizing process. As with any manual data collection, remote digitizing is subjective. The mapping results will vary depending on the digitizer's knowledge of riverscape process and experience with GIS software and imagery interpretation. Despite these challenges, it is important to recognize that most monitoring approaches face similar administrative and technical obstacles. Ultimately, the value of high-quality monitoring data far exceeds that of logistical challenges.

Remote sensing technologies like drones and satellites open many doors for large- and small-scale monitoring and assessment. Since this field of research is relatively new, there is ample opportunity for new innovative techniques that overcome the subjectivity, data storage, and spatiotemporal limitations of this protocol. The rise of artificial intelligence is allowing for implementation of object-based image analysis (OBIA) that uses a training algorithm and calibration data to classify features based on groups of pixel values and their orientations (Macfarlane et al., 2017). Satellite imagery is increasing in spatiotemporal resolution and accessibility, allowing for medium resolution, regional analysis without the logistical challenges of field work and drone flights.

Looking ahead, one of the most promising applications of this drone-based monitoring protocol is its potential for repeat data capture during critical events that test riverscape resilience—such as 100-year floods, extreme droughts, or following wildfires and debris flows. Our method is particularly well-suited for recording pre- and post-restoration conditions, enabling long-term monitoring of the effectiveness of restoration efforts. The findings from this study, along with future applications of this protocol, will contribute to the growing body of research validating the cruciality of structural complexity for healthy riverscapes.

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